

Reconstructing CT Images from HU Intervals: A Simple Applied Project

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Abstract

Computed Tomography (CT) images play a crucial role in medical diagnostics, with each voxel representing tissue density values in Hounsfield Units (HU). While filtering CT images by HU ranges simplifies the analysis, it also leads to information loss. This work explores the feasibility of reconstructing CT images from their filtered versions using three model architectures: a small neural network receiving individual voxels, a neural network receiving a column of voxels, and a small 3D convolutional neural network receiving a cube of voxels. Each model reconstructs individual or small groups of voxels iteratively to form the complete 3D image. All models produced high-quality reconstructions. However, differences in reconstruction quality, speed and reliability were observed. The viability of this model has promising implications for generative artificial intelligence in medical imaging, potentially enabling the creation of generative models that produce high-quality images with reduced computational complexity.

1 Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) shows great promise in the medical field by accelerating and automating diagnostics. However, limited access to medical data, due to high acquisition costs and privacy regulations, hinders the development of AI models. Generative AI can help address this challenge by creating synthetic medical images to augment datasets without compromising privacy or requiring expensive data collection. However, generating medical images, especially high-resolution 3D images like those from CT scans, presents a unique challenge due to the complexity and fine detail of these images.

CT scans are widely used in the medical field, providing detailed cross-sectional views of the body. Each voxel in a CT image represents tissue density in Hounsfield Units (HU), a standardized scale ranging from -1000 HU (air) to values above 1000 HU (denser structures). By adjusting the HU range, clinicians can isolate specific tissues for analysis, e.g. lower HU ranges focus on lung tissue, while higher HU values highlight bones.

This project proposes a model that reconstructs CT images from their HU range filtered versions. If successful, this approach could have significant potential in generative AI for medical imaging, as it may lead to models that focus on generating these filtered versions rather than reconstructing the entire CT image in one step. These versions would then be combined to form a CT image using the model developed in this project. Since the filtered versions contain less information than the original image, this could lead to simpler generative models and faster image generation while still maintaining high image quality.

To our knowledge, no prior research has explored reconstructing CT images from their HU-filtered versions.

2 Material and Methods

Figure 1 illustrates the expected inputs and outputs of the reconstruction model, along with its training workflow. First, a CT image is filtered using different Hounsfield Unit ranges, each showcasing different tissues and structures. Then, these images, or parts of them, are passed to the reconstruction model, which subsequently generates an image that is compared against the original. The similarity is measured by a loss function, which is used to update the model's parameters.

The derivation of a general expression to recover the CT image from its filtered counterparts was explored, but it proved challenging due to information loss when using non-contiguous HU ranges for filtering.

Figure 1: Workflow for training the reconstruction model. (Top left) Slice of a CT image and (Top right) filtered versions of that slice using different HU ranges. The image generated by the reconstruction model (Bottom center) should closely resemble the original CT image.

2.1 Dataset and Pre-Processing

The dataset used in this project is the Lung Image Database Consortium image collection (LIDC-IDRI) [1], containing 1,018 CT scans. To prepare the data, each CT scan was first converted to HU, when necessary. The scans were then filtered based on specific HU ranges using a clipping and scaling operation: values below and above the lower and upper HU limits were set to 0 and 1, respectively, while values within the range were scaled between 0 and 1. After filtering, the scans were normalized to a range of 0 to 1 to serve as ground truth during training. To ensure uniformity, each scan was limited to 30 slices, with each slice rescaled to 128x128 pixels.

2.2 Model Architecture and Training

Analyzing a full 3D image at once requires a large and complex model architecture, which can result in extended training times and unnecessary complexity. To address this, an alternative approach was explored, focusing on models that incrementally reconstruct small groups of voxels or individual voxels. By applying the model sequentially to each voxel or voxel group, the full image is reconstructed step by step. This approach reduces model complexity and training time. The key challenge then becomes determining the most suitable input format for the model.

Three types of inputs were tested: single voxels, columns of voxels, and cubes of voxels. The column and cube of voxels contain contextual information, whereas the single voxel does not. Figure 2 illustrates these types of input data.

Three models were evaluated, each corresponding to one of the input types. A hyper-parameter search was conducted for each model.

Figure 2: Representation of the type of input data received by each model.

Model	Average Loss	σ Loss	Reconstruction Time (s)
NNVoxel	0.0024	0.0108	5.7
NNColumn	0.0007	0.0011	0.35
ConvCube	0.0007	0.0014	12.8

Table 1: Statistics of the models.

- **NNVoxel:** A small neural network that takes filtered versions of a voxel as input and outputs a single voxel. *Hyper-parameter search:* neural networks with 1 to 3 layers were tested, with each layer having between 2 to 4 neurons.
- **NNColumn:** A neural network that takes filtered versions of a column of voxels spanning several slices of a scan as input and outputs the corresponding column. *Hyper-parameter search:* neural networks with 1 to 5 layers were tested, with each layer consisting of 30 to 100 neurons.
- **ConvCube:** A small convolutional network that takes a cube of voxels as input and outputs the center voxel of the cube. The model includes a single convolutional layer with a kernel size matching the input cube, followed by a neural network. *Hyper-parameter search:* neural networks with 1 to 3 layers were tested, with each layer containing between 1 and 6 neurons; the input cube width varied from 3 to 7 units per side.

All models were evaluated using the same combinations of HU ranges. These ranges were selected to ensure diversity of structures and types of tissue. Some of these combination of ranges are shown in Figure 3.

Batch normalization was employed in all models. ReLU activation functions were used in the intermediate layers, with sigmoid activation applied in the output layers to constrain the outputs between 0 and 1. Since the models operate on small regions or individual voxels, mean squared error (MSE) was selected as the loss function. Perceptual losses, which assess structural similarity, were not considered appropriate for this approach. A validation set and test set were created, each comprising 15% of the data, with the remaining images used for training.

3 Results

With a sufficient number of HU ranges, all three models produced high-quality reconstructions that were very similar to the original images. Most hyper-parameter combinations produced similar results. Table 1 provides statistics for the best-performing model of each type, including the average and standard deviation of validation loss, as well as the average reconstruction time for each model. Notable differences between the models include:

- **Quality:** NNColumn and ConvCube delivered the best performance, as expected, since these models incorporated more contextual information from neighboring voxels. However, upon visual inspection, the differences in reconstruction detail between the three models were often minor.
- **Speed:** NNColumn was significantly faster than the other two models, as anticipated, since it produced multiple voxels simultaneously, improving efficiency.
- **Reliability:** NNvoxel exhibited greater instability during training, with more pronounced loss oscillations, indicating inconsistencies in reconstruction quality across different images. This is further

Figure 3: (Left) Filtered versions of a scan and (Right) the original and the reconstructed scan produced by the NNColumn model.

supported by a higher standard deviation in the loss. NNColumn and ConvCube seemed more reliable, displaying more consistent loss trends.

Based on the evaluation, NNColumn was selected as the top-performing model, offering the best balance of speed, reliability, and reconstruction quality.

The HU ranges used had a significant impact on reconstruction quality. Figure 3 shows the results of the NNColumn model when using different sets of HU ranges. Models with fewer HU ranges produced coarser, less detailed images, as expected. The combination of HU ranges that yielded the best results included a higher number of ranges. In this case, the reconstruction was very good, with lung tissue appearing slightly denser in the reconstructed image compared to the original, and the exterior tissues showcasing some granularity. Ideally, the number of HU ranges should be minimized to reduce the size of any potential generative model that requires this model in the generative process. Rather than increasing the number of HU ranges, refining them may also lead to better image quality.

4 Conclusions

Training a reconstruction model for CT images from filtered HU range versions was successful, achieving the project's goal. All tested models produced high-quality images, but the selected model maintained both image quality and excellent reconstruction speed. This reconstruction model is expected to be valuable in generative medical AI projects, where generating realistic CT images can be simplified by first creating filtered versions, followed by using the reconstruction model to restore the complete image.

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